

DETECTION OF TRANSVERSE CRACKS IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES BY EMBEDDED PLASTIC OPTICAL FIBERS

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SUMMARY: In this paper, tensile and three-point bending tests were conducted for GFRP laminates with embedded plastic optical fibers. Transverse cracks in GFRP laminates were observed by a video microscope. As the strain increased, the optical power decreased linearly before the initiation of transverse cracks, but nonlinear decrease appeared after that. There was no damage of the optical fiber before final failure of the specimen. Therefore, it is concluded that the nonlinearly change of the optical power loss was affected by the transverse cracks. Then, it is considered that plastic optical fibers have much potential to be used as transverse crack detecting sensors for smart composites. Simulated results by using a three-dimensional ray tracing model were compared with the experimental results, and it was found that the nonlinear change of the optical power loss was strongly affected by the deformation near a crack.

KEYWORDS: Plastic fiber sensor, Damage sensor, Transverse crack detection, Smart composite

INTRODUCTION

An optical fiber sensor has been developed for a sensor of smart structures and materials because of the small size, low weight, geometrical flexibility and so on. Smart structures and materials where optical fibers are embedded / attached have capabilities of real-time health-monitoring or simple and fast examination. The nondestructive evaluations by using optical fibers have been conducted through detecting cracks or measuring changes in strain, stress and temperature.

The cracks in materials can be detected when embedded optical fibers are broken by the cracks. In this case, optical fibers can detect only initial occurrence of cracks because the transmitted power in the fibers decreases to zero due to fractures by a few cracks. For long fiber reinforced composite materials, cracks often occur in the direction normal to reinforced fibers.

Fig. 1: An optical fiber embedded in composite laminates

Therefore, optical fibers should be embedded in the direction normal to the crack surface (Fig. 1(a)). However, in this configuration, matrix rich area around optical fibers may cause initiation of transverse cracks and the material strength may decrease. As far as the strength is concerned, it is preferable to embed optical fibers along reinforced fibers.

For long fiber reinforced composite laminates, transverse cracks are most serious damages. Transverse cracks in 90° plies of cross-ply FRP laminates do not generally grow into 0° plies. Therefore, when optical fibers are embedded along reinforced fibers in 0° plies, transverse cracks do not cut optical fibers (Fig. 1(b)). However if transverse cracks in 90° plies influence the optical behavior of the optical fibers, they can be used as a health monitoring sensor of the laminates.

One of the authors has been successfully establishing a micromechanical model for transverse crack initiation and growth in composite laminates based on the in-situ microscopic observation experiments of coupon specimens^{1,2,3}. If such transverse crack initiation and growth can be detected by optical fibers qualitatively, our micromechanical model can predict the following damage growth and the residual strength and life.

A plastic optical fiber was selected as an embedded optical fiber sensor. Plastic optical fibers are much cheaper and easier to connect than silica fibers, but because of the large loss, they are used for short distance communication, illumination, etc. They are multi-mode fibers and can be also used as a damage sensor by measuring optical power loss. As a sensor for smart composites, they have advantages suitable to be embedded in FRP because of the similarity of its elasticity and coefficients of thermal expansion. Plastic optical fibers also have much higher failure strain than general FRP, so that they will not be broken near cracks at large strain. When the cracks are generated, the strain field near a crack is changed. Then, it is considered that the optical power propagating through the plastic optical fiber decreases if it is embedded near the cracks.

In this paper, tensile and bending tests of GFRP cross-ply laminates with embedded plastic optical fibers were conducted. For tensile tests, the relations among the optical power, strain and transverse crack density were obtained experimentally. The experimental results were compared with numerical simulations based on an optical fiber theory. For bending tests, the relations among the optical power, deflection and number of transverse cracks were obtained experimentally. The relation between optical power loss and transverse cracks are discussed.

EXPERIMENTS

Specimen

Parameters of plastic optical fibers (ESCA CK10, Mitsubishi Rayon Co., Ltd.) used in this paper are shown in Table 1. The material properties of the GFRP lamina where optical fibers were embedded is shown in Table 2, where direction 1 is along reinforced fibers. For all specimens, plastic optical fibers were embedded in the center of 0° plies along reinforced fibers. The thickness of one 0° ply was approximately $80 \mu\text{m}$.

Dimensions of specimens are shown in Table 3 with stacking sequences. Type A, B, C and D specimens were used for tensile tests and Type E and F specimens were used for bending tests. A schematic view of specimens for tensile tests are shown in Fig. 2. Aluminum tabs were attached on the specimen used for tensile tests out of the region where an optical fiber was embedded to avoid the effects of cramping pressure to the power loss. Strain gages were attached at the center of the specimens. Type C specimens have a single initial crack at the center in the top ply (Fig. 3). Type C specimens were used to study the effect of a single crack in 90° plies to the optical power loss. Schematic views of cross sections of Type B, D

Table 1: Parameters of plastic optical fiber

Parameters		Values
Core	Material	PMMA
	Radius	$120 \mu\text{m}$
	Young's modulus	3.09 GPa
	Poisson's ratio	0.3
Clad	Material	Fluoropolymer
	Radius	$125 \mu\text{m}$
	Young's modulus	0.68 GPa
	Poisson's ratio	0.3
Wave number		660 nm

Table 2: Parameters of GFRP prepreg

Parameters	Values
E_1	14.4 GPa
E_2	4.30 GPa
G_{12}	1.54 GPa
G_{23}	0.817 GPa
ν_{12}	0.362

Table 3: Dimension of specimens

Type	w (mm)	h (mm)	t (mm)	Stacking Sequence
A	6	100	0.4	$[0^\circ_5]$
B	6	100	0.4	$[90^\circ/0^\circ_3/90^\circ]$
C	6	100	0.4	$[0^\circ_5]$ with an initial crack
D	20	140	0.9	$[0^\circ_3/90^\circ_6/0^\circ_3]$
E	10	40	1.5	$[0^\circ_{18}]$
F	10	40	1.5	$[90^\circ_6/0^\circ_6/90^\circ_6]$

Fig. 2: Schematic view of specimen (Type A, B, C, D)

Fig. 3: Initial crack of Type C specimen

Fig. 4: Schematic view of cross section of specimen (Type B, D, F)

Fig. 5: Schematic view of fabrication of specimen

and F are shown in Fig. 4. Optical fibers embedded in 0° plies contacted to 90° plies. Specimens were fabricated by hot press method. Prepregs, where an optical fiber was embedded, were cut as shown in Fig. 5 to avoid to generate matrix rich regions.

Experimental Setup

The experimental setup is shown in Fig. 6. The light from a LED (Light Emitting Diode, wave length $\lambda = 660$ nm) was focused through a lens and incident into a plastic optical fiber. The light through the optical fiber was incident into a PD (Photo Detector) and the optical power was measured by an optical power meter. The load was measured by a load cell and recorded by PC (Personal Computer). For tensile tests, strains were also measured by strain gages attached on the specimen. The top surface of Type A specimen and the side surface of Type D and F specimens were observed to count the number of transverse cracks in 90° plies

Fig. 6: Experimental setup

with a video microscope under loading.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Experimental results of Type A, B, C specimens

Tensile tests of Type A, B and C specimens were conducted at a crosshead speed of 0.12 mm/min or 1.2 mm/min. Some leakage of the light was observed at the cracks for Type B specimen. Therefore, we could count the number of transverse cracks not only in the top ply but also in the bottom ply by observing the leaky light through 0° plies from the bottom ply.

The relation between the optical power normalized by the initial power and the strain is shown in Fig. 7 for the Type A and Type B specimens. The transverse crack density of Type B specimen is also plotted against the strain in Fig. 7. It is shown that the optical power loss is very small without cracks (Type A specimen) and the optical power decreases linearly. For Type B specimens, the optical power decreased linearly until the strain reached 1.0 %, and then nonlinearly up to 2.5 % after cracks initiated at 1.0 %. At approximately 2.5 %, the specimen was broken. The optical power loss without cracks also depends on the stacking sequence or the dimension of specimens.

The broken specimen were cut along the optical fiber after the tensile test and it is confirmed that the embedded optical fiber was not broken at the crack tips. Therefore, it is concluded that the nonlinear increase of the optical power loss results from the transverse cracks in the 90° plies.

An experimental result of Type C specimen was shown in Fig. 8 with that of Type A specimen. The optical power loss by a single crack was very small. Then, it is difficult to know quantitatively the effect on optical power loss by a single crack. However, it should be noted that a single crack affects the nonlinearity of optical power loss.

Experimental results of Type D Specimens

Tensile tests of Type D specimens were conducted at a crosshead speed of 0.75 mm/min. In this test, the side of specimen was observed by a video microscope to count transverse cracks

Fig. 7: Relation among optical power, crack density and strain (Type A and B specimens)

Fig. 8: Relation between optical power and strain (Type A and C specimens)

in 0° plies because the leaky light from transverse cracks in 0° plies could not be observed in this stacking sequence.

The relation among the optical power, the crack density and the strain is shown in Fig. 9 for the Type D specimen. The optical power decreased nonlinearly after initiation of transverse cracks and the behavior of optical power loss was similar to that of Type B specimen. The optical power loss by transverse cracks in Type D specimens is smaller than that in Type B specimens. This is considered due to the fact that the 0° plies of Type D specimens is inner and the local deformation near crack tip is smaller than that of Type B specimens.

Experimental results of Type E and F Specimens

Three-points bending tests of Type E and F specimens were conducted at a crosshead speed of 1.5 mm/min. Here, the length of span is 30 mm and the side of specimen was observed to count number of cracks by a video microscope under loading. The deflection at the loading point was obtained from the crosshead displacement.

The relation between the optical power and the deflection d is shown in Fig. 10 for the Type E and F specimens. The number of transverse cracks occurred in bottom 90° plies (tensile side) of Type F specimens are also plotted in Fig. 10. When there were no transverse cracks (Type E specimen), the optical power decreased linearly up to the deflection of about 5 mm. For Type F specimens, on the other hand, the optical power decreased nonlinearly after the deflection of 2 mm or occurrence of the 5th crack. The number of cracks did not increase more than 10. The delamination at the interface between 0° plies and bottom 90° plies also observed.

Fig. 9: Relation among optical power, crack density and strain (Type D specimen)

Fig. 10: Relation among optical power, number of crack and deflection (Type E and F specimen)

Fig. 11: Relation between optical power loss by cracks and strain (Type B specimens)

Fig. 12: Relation between optical power loss by cracks and crack density (Type B specimens)

DISCUSSION

Effect of transverse cracks on optical power loss in tensile tests

An optical power loss L (dB) of the optical fiber embedded into cross-ply laminates in tension is represented as a function of strain. Supposing that L is written as a linear combination of a loss without a crack and a loss induced by transverse cracks, the total optical loss can be described as,

$$L(\varepsilon) = L_0(\varepsilon) + L_c(\varepsilon) \quad (1)$$

where L_0 is a loss by tensile strain without a crack, L_c is a loss induced by transverse cracks. For Type B specimens, L_0 was obtained from the optical power curve of Type B specimens in the strain range from 0.0 % to 1.3 % as a linear regression curve, and then L_0 was obtained by subtracting L_0 from L (Fig. 11). In tensile tests, we suppose that $N(\varepsilon) = \rho(\varepsilon)h$ is the number of transverse cracks, h is the length of specimen and L_{sc} is a loss by a single transverse crack. N is actually a discontinuous function, but it is assumed to be a continuous function of the strain in this section. The relation between L_c and transverse crack density is also shown in Fig. 12. If dependence of L_{sc} on strain is weak enough to be negligible, the relation between L_{sc} and transverse crack density should be linear. However the L_c increases nonlinearly when $\rho > 0.8$ ($\varepsilon > 2.1$ %). Then, it is concluded that the optical power loss by a single transverse crack increases nonlinearly in the range of large strain and the nonlinearity is caused by the local deformation of an optical fiber or local change of refractive index distribution near a crack tip.

Here the effect of local deformation is studied by using a three-dimensional finite element method (FEM) and a ray tracing method. The model of a ray propagating in the deformed fiber embedded in the GFRP near the crack is shown in Fig. 13. The length of deformed section by a crack is defined by d . The cross section of an embedded optical fiber is assumed to be deformed to an ellipse whose major axis is $a(z)$, minor axis is $b(z)$ and center coordinate is $(x_0(z), y_0(z))$. The deformation of a fiber near a crack is calculated by using a three-dimensional finite element method (FEM).

Fig. 13: Ray propagating in deformed optical fiber near crack tip Fig.14: Ray through the small element

The behavior of a light propagating through the fiber is simulated by a three dimensional ray tracing method. Rays through the small element at $z = 0$ are shown in Fig. 14. The (r, θ) coordinate is not a cylindrical system and defined by

$$x = ra_0 \cos \theta, y = rb_0 \sin \theta \quad (2)$$

where, $a_0 = a(0)$ and $b_0 = b(0)$. The critical angle θ_c is defined by

$$\sin \alpha_c = n_{cl}/n_{co} = \cos \theta_c \quad (3)$$

where n_{cl} and n_{co} are refractive indexes of a clad and a core of the fiber, respectively. Rays are reflected at the boundary between a core and a clad of the fiber (in Fig.15). Here, $\tilde{x}\tilde{y}\tilde{z}$ is a local coordinates system fixed to the boundary, $\tilde{\alpha}$ is an incident angle, $\theta_{\tilde{z}}$ and $\theta_{\tilde{y}}$ are angles from \tilde{z} and \tilde{y} axes to a ray respectively and $\rho_{\tilde{z}}$ and $\rho_{\tilde{y}}$ are radiuses of curvature of boundary plane in respect to \tilde{z} and \tilde{y} axes, respectively. The $\theta_{\tilde{z}}$, $\theta_{\tilde{y}}$ and $\tilde{\alpha}$ are functions of r , θ , θ_0 and θ_f . The $P_i (i = 1, 2, \dots)$ is the position where the ray reflects. The power reflection rate T_i at P_i is defined as follows^{4, 5}:

Fig.15: Rays reflected at the boundary between core and clad

Fig.16: Relation between optical power loss by a single transverse crack and strain

$$T_i = \begin{cases} 1 & 0 \leq \theta_z < \theta_c \\ T_r (< 1) & 0 \leq \tilde{\alpha} < \alpha_c \\ T_t (< 1) & \theta_c \leq \theta_z < \pi/2 \text{ and } \alpha_c \leq \tilde{\alpha} < \pi/2 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$T_r = 1 - \frac{4 \cos \tilde{\alpha} (\cos^2 \tilde{\alpha} - \cos^2 \alpha_c)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{\left\{ \cos \tilde{\alpha} + (\cos^2 \tilde{\alpha} - \cos^2 \alpha_c)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\}^2} \quad (5)$$

$$T_t = 1 - \frac{4 \cos \tilde{\alpha} (\sin^2 \tilde{\alpha} - \sin^2 \alpha_c)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{\cos^2 \alpha_c} \exp \left\{ -\frac{4\pi}{3\lambda} \bar{\rho} \frac{(\sin^2 \tilde{\alpha} - \sin^2 \alpha_c)^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\sin^2 \tilde{\alpha}} \right\} \quad (6)$$

$$\bar{\rho} = \frac{\rho_y \rho_z \sin^2 \tilde{\alpha}}{\rho_y \cos^2 \theta_z + \rho_z \cos^2 \theta_y}$$

where T_r is a power reflection rate of refracting rays, T_t is a power reflection rate of tunneling rays and λ is a wavelength of the light. When $0 \leq \theta_z < \theta_c$, rays are reflected perfectly and called bound rays. The power of refracting and tunneling rays are leaked. The total optical power of light through a fiber is calculated by the following equation.

$$I_{total} = 2a_0 b_0 \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta_\phi \int_0^{\theta_c} d\theta_0 \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} d\theta \int_0^{a_0} I_0 \prod_i T_i r dr \quad (7)$$

The calculated results of the optical power loss by a single transverse crack are shown in Fig. 16. The experimental optical power loss curves obtained for Type B and Type C specimens are also plotted against the strain in Fig. 17. The curve of Type B specimen was obtained by the equation of $L_{sc}(\epsilon) = L_c(\epsilon)/\rho(\epsilon)h$ ($\rho > 0$). The estimation of optical power loss is larger than experimental results but the behavior qualitatively agrees with the experimental result of Type C specimen. It is considered that the difference of behavior between Type B and Type C specimens results from the difference in the crack distance $1/\rho$ and the stacking sequence.

Effect of transverse crack in bending tests

The relation among L_c , number of cracks and deflection is shown in Fig. 17. After $\delta = 3.5$ mm, number of transverse crack did not increase. However, gradients of the curve before and after $\delta = 3.5$ mm were almost same. This means that there was no clear correlation between number of cracks and optical power loss in bending tests. Then, $L_{sc} \neq NL_c$ in bending tests. Delamination was observed at the interface between 0° and bottom 90° plies and the effect of

Fig.17: Relation among optical power loss, number of cracks and strain in bending test delamination cannot be ignored.

CONCLUSIONS

Tensile and three-point bending tests of GFRP laminates with an embedded plastic optical fiber were conducted. It is experimentally confirmed that the optical power decreases nonlinearly after the initiation of transverse cracks when the specimen is loaded in tension or bending. From the experimental results, it is considered that the optical power loss in tensile tests depends on number of cracks but the dependence in bending tests is small. An embedded plastic optical fiber can be used to detect the number of transverse cracks in cross-ply laminates, and also in general laminates.

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